

“DEVELOPMENT OF REGIONAL DISPARITIES IN LATUR DISTRICT”

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Abstract

The present paper aims to evaluate the levels of regional development of Latur district in Maharashtra. The entire paper is based on secondary sources of data. Data has been processed and analyze by statistical technique such as co-efficient index and composite index of development (CID). Data has been represented through the Choropleth map. For this research purpose a tahsil unit of Latur district is considered. The purpose of this study is to remove the disparities and inequalities between the developed and backward regions. In order to bring out, the region under study from the various kind of disparities and imbalances regional development, an attempt has been made here to find out different levels of development with the study area. The regional planners and policy makers take into consideration, the diagnostic plan on priority basis to eliminate the regional imbalances and disparities to make the region socially and economically balanced.

Keywords: *Levels of Development, Co-efficient of development, Composite Index.*

Introduction:

Regional development is the result of interaction between various economic and social institutional factors. The task of regional planning is to prepare a comprehensive regional development plan, an integrated and co-ordinate plan between the physical, economic and social components that is between different levels of development in the region.

The disparities and imbalances in natural conditions in terms of terrain, climate such as temperature, rainfall, soil type, drainage, forest, minerals, transport and communication network etc. lead to imbalance socio-economic development. Even a small micro level region like Latur district does not have homogeneous social and economic development. There are some areas which are better developed due to favourable natural conditions, while others are socially and economically much backward.

The change, either positive or negative directions, provides an understanding of the region to consider for socio-economic planning. With the help of change in the socio-economic conditions, one may diagnose the region for planning. The term change often is used for both positive as well as the negative sense. Here, we are concerned to understand various aspects associated with socio-economic conditions of the study area and to find the levels of different regions with the district at tahsil levels and to diagnose these regions with the help of certain indices for the planning to uplift such region, which are socially and economically, lag behind. It is in fact, natural phenomena that all the regions on the earth are not equally endowed with the natural resources. Some regions are fortunate

to have a favorable natural condition, which others, at the same time do not have. So here an attempt has been made to study the levels of development in the study region.

STUDY AREA:

Latur district has been selected for the present investigation. The study region is situated in the south-east part of the Maharashtra and it lies between 17° 52' north latitude to 18° 50' north latitudes and 76° 12' east longitudes to 77° 18' east longitudes.

It is bounded on the north by Beed and Parbhani districts, on the north-east by Nanded district, on the south-east and south by the Karnataka state and on the north-west, west and south by Osmanabad district. For administrative purpose the district is divided into two revenue divisions i.e. Latur and Udgir division and in 10 tahsils Viz. Latur, Ausa, Renapur, Udgir, Ahmadpur, Chakur, Nilanga, Deoni, Jalkot and Shirur-Anantpal. Deoni, Jalkot and Shirur-Anantpal tahsils are newly created tahsils (Fig. 1.1).

The total geographical area of Latur district is 7157 sq.km. and it covers 2.39 per cent of the total geographical area of Maharashtra.

OBJECTIVES:

The basic objective of the paper is to study the levels of regional development of the Latur district. Further, to analyze them basically to the geographical point of view.

DATABASE AND METHODOLOGY:

The study is entirely based on secondary sources of data. The required essential data has been collected from the District Census Handbook, Latur and Socio-economic Review of Latur District (2010).

There are different ways to calculate the index of levels of development. Different socio-economic variables have been selected to determine the levels of development. Sixteen following variables have been selected to identify the levels of development.

- 1) Population density
- 2) Sex ratio
- 3) Percentage of general literacy
- 4) Percentage of urban population to total population
- 5) Percentage of work participation rate
- 6) Percentage of population engaged in secondary and tertiary activities to total population.
- 7) Percentage of cultivable area to total area.
- 8) Percentage of irrigated area to total cultivable area.
- 9) Percentage of villages having educational facilities.
- 10) Percentage of villages having medical facilities.
- 11) Percentage of rural population served by weekly market facility.
- 12) Percentage of co-operative agricultural society facility to total Population.
- 13) Percentage of villages having post offices.
- 14) Percentage of villages having bank facilities.

- 15) Percentage of villages having approach by pucca road facility
 16) Percentage of service centres to total villages

The method adopted to determine levels of development evolves two stages, first determination of levels of development of tahsil in terms of discrete variables and then integration of the values obtained to give a composite index of development taking all the variables into account. The co-efficient of a tahsil in terms of a single variable is expressed as :

$$CDI = \frac{P_i}{PI} \times 100$$

Where,

CDI = The co-efficient of development for variable i,

P_i = Percentage of variable i, in the area unit.

PI = Mean Percentage of variable i, in the study region.

By summing the development indices taking into account all variables. We get composite index of development by following equation.

$$CID = \frac{CDI_1 + CDI_2 + CDI_3 + \dots + CDI_n}{N}$$

Where,

CID = Composite index of development.

N = Number of variables

Levels of development are thus calculated for all ten tahsils on the basis of above formula. The composite development indices so obtained are given in the Table 1.1.

Table 1.1
 Latur District - Composite Index of Development

Sl.No	Tahsil	CDI	CID	Classification
1	Latur	2342.53	146.40	High
2	Ranapur	1534.28	95.89	Low
3	Amrapur	1493.89	93.36	Low
4	Jalga	1261.94	78.87	Low
5	Chikar	1480.53	92.53	Low
6	Shinar Arantpal	1460.44	91.27	Low
7	Ausa	1707.04	106.69	Mediate
8	Nilarga	1758.45	109.90	Mediate
9	Devri	1487.34	92.95	Low
10	Ulghir	2085.56	130.34	High

Source : Compiled by the Author

SPATIAL ANALYSIS OF THE LEVELS OF DEVELOPMENT:

The composite indices of development for all tahsils have been treated statistically and three tier classifications of levels of development is determined as high, moderate and low level of development. The regional levels of development have been shown in Fig.1.2.

1. High Levels of Development:

The high levels of development is observed only in central part of the study region. Two tahsils namely Latur and Udgir are recorded high levels of development. It comprises 24.70 percent of total geographical area and contain 23.81 percent of the total service centres of the entire region.

The area of these tahsils is highly endowed with fertile soils. These tahsils are endowed with favourable position in regard to irrigation facilities, medical facilities, high density of population, co-operative societies, post office service. In this high developed area the percentage of urban population is more. The development of transport is found more.

2. Moderate Levels of Development:

Nilanga and Ausa tahsils are included in the group of moderate level of development. It covers 32.33 percent of the total geographical area of 34.53 percent of the total service centres. So far as the service centres in the tahsils are considered they are smaller in size and more in number than the previous category. This region has better irrigation facilities and fertile soil. They have well co-operative societies because this area is agriculturally developed. This region has better work participation rate, urban proportion and transportation facilities.

3. Low Levels of Development

The spatial analysis of levels of development shows that low level of development is found in Renapur, Ahmedpur, Jalkot, Chakur, Shirur Anantpal and Deoni tahsils. In these tahsils the number of service centres are more and smaller in size in this group. It covers 42.98 percent of the total geographical area and 41.67 percent of the total service centres. Most of the central and north eastern part is included in this category. Though more land is available for cultivation, poor irrigation facilities have retarded the progress of this area. In these tahsils transport facilities, medical facilities, literacy are inadequate (Table 1.1).

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS:

It is concluded here that Latur and Udgir tahsils has scored maximum in sixteen of the indices. These tahsils are situated in western and eastern part of the district especially in Manjara basin they attained high levels of development and found densely populated area. The area of these tahsils is highly endowed with fertile soils. These tahsils are endowed with favourable position in regard to irrigation facilities. In this high developed area the percentage of urban population is more. The development of transport is found more.

Nilanga and Ausa tahsils are included in the group of moderate level of development. This region has better irrigation facilities and fertile soil. They have well co-operative societies because this area is agriculturally developed.

Therefore, Renapur, Ahmedpur, Jalkot, Chakur, Shirur Anantpal and Deoni tahsils are be-

ing low levels of development. It is essential to note here that there is need to proper planning for the development of these lower ranked tahsils. Whenever, preference can be given firstly to socio-economic facilities.

The last vital task is to critically examine the performance of the demoted tahsils of Renapur and Ahmedpur to put suggestions for exaltation of their standards. Similarly, the upgraded tahsils should also be given proper incentive for further enhancement of their achievements which would be beneficial for their development as well as the district.

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